

A SEMIBLIND APPROACH TO OPTIMUM MULTIUSER DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

A novel multiuser *semiblind* demodulation scheme is proposed. Channel estimation is carried out according to the Maximum Likelihood (ML) principle and using the Expectation Maximization (EM) algorithm. Afterwards, the channel state information is used to implement the joint optimum detector with a dynamic programming algorithm (e.g. the Viterbi algorithm). The resulting demodulator is termed *semiblind* because the statistical features of the received signals are exploited together with the *a priori* knowledge of a very small number of transmitted symbols. Computer simulations show that the proposed scheme leads to practically optimum performance in Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) time dispersive channels.

1 INTRODUCTION

CDMA is the basic multiple access scheme to be used in third generation wireless communication systems [1]. The capacity of current CDMA systems is severely limited by the Multiple Access Interference (MAI) due to the multiple users sharing the channel and Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) caused by frequency-selective fading. As a consequence, it is foreseen that future wireless receivers will incorporate sophisticated coding and signal processing capabilities in order to achieve high data rates [1].

The optimum CDMA joint multiuser receiver results from the Maximum Likelihood (ML) detection of the symbols transmitted by all system users [2]. This receiver requires full knowledge of the multiuser channel parameters, that have to be accurately estimated. Supervised channel estimation techniques rely on the transmission of *a priori* known symbols (referred as a *training sequence*) within every transmitted data block but this is very inefficient for many applications. Subspace-based approaches have been recently proposed (see [3] and references therein) that perform channel estimation in a *blind* manner, i.e., without the transmission of training sequences. These methods, however, are computationally stringent, require the transmission of large data blocks and exhibits poor convergence in the low Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) region.

Figure 1: Baseband discrete-time equivalent model of a DS CDMA system with time dispersive channels.

We propose a new approach to joint multiuser demodulation that consists of the successive *semiblind* estimation of the multiuser channel parameters and the transmitted symbols in the ML sense. Channel estimation is performed using the Expectation-Maximization (EM) method [4] and symbol detection is carried out with a dynamic programming algorithm [2]. A decision directed EM channel estimation algorithm is also introduced. The proposed demodulators are termed *semiblind* because they exploit both the statistical knowledge of the received signals and the transmission of training sequences. The main advantage over supervised approaches is that very short training sequences are enough to attain practically optimum performance. Blind subspace approaches are outperformed because the proposed demodulator works efficiently even for very small data blocks and low SNR.

The remaining of the paper is organized as follows. Next section describes the signal model of the time-dispersive multiuser CDMA channel. Section 3 presents the channel estimation algorithms. ML multiuser detection is studied in section 4. Illustrative computer simulation results are shown in section 5 and, finally, section 6 is devoted to the conclusions.

2 SIGNAL MODEL

Figure 1 shows the baseband discrete-time equivalent model of a Direct Sequence (DS) CDMA system with time dispersive channels. When the i -th user transmits an isolated symbol, s_i , it is multiplied by a unique binary-valued spreading sequence with L chips per symbol, $c_i(k)$ $k = 0, \dots, L - 1$. The resulting signal passes through a linear time-dispersive channel,

$h_i(k)$ $k = 0, \dots, P - 1$, and the received sequence is the superposition of the transmitted signals from the N users plus the Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) sequence $g(k)$, i.e.,

$$x(k) = \sum_{i=1}^N d_i(k)s_i + g(k), \quad k = 0, \dots, L + P - 2. \quad (1)$$

The sequence $d_i(k) = c_i(k) * h_i(k) = \sum_{p=0}^{P-1} h_i(p)c_i(k-p)$, has length $L + P - 1$ and will be termed *received code*. Due to the channel time dispersive effect, when a stream of symbols is transmitted, $s_i(n)$ interferes with $s_i(n-1)$, $s_i(n-2)$, $\dots$, $s_i(n-m+1)$, where $m = \lceil \frac{L+P-1}{L} \rceil$ is the channel memory size. Therefore, the overall received sequence is

$$\begin{aligned} x(n, k) &= x(nL + k) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} d_i(r, k)s_i(n-r) + g(k) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $k = 0, \dots, L - 1$ and $d_i(r, k) = d_i(rL + k)$.

Using vector notation, the observations in (2) can be written as

$$\mathbf{x}(n) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \underline{\mathbf{D}}(r)\underline{\mathbf{s}}(n-r) + \mathbf{g}(n) = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{s}(n) + \mathbf{g}(n) \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(n) = [x(n, 0), \dots, x(n, L - 1)]^T$, $\mathbf{D} = [\underline{\mathbf{D}}(m-1) \ \dots \ \underline{\mathbf{D}}(0)]$ is the $L \times Nm$ received code matrix, composed of the submatrices $\underline{\mathbf{D}}(r) = [\mathbf{d}_1(r) \ \dots \ \mathbf{d}_N(r)]$ and $\mathbf{d}_i(r) = [d_i(r, 0), \dots, d_i(r, L - 1)]^T$. The transmitted symbol vectors $\underline{\mathbf{s}}(l) = [s_1(l), \dots, s_N(l)]^T$, $l = n - m + 1, \dots, n$ are stacked to construct the $Nm \times 1$ received symbol vector $\mathbf{s}(n) = [\underline{\mathbf{s}}^T(n-m+1) \ \dots \ \underline{\mathbf{s}}^T(n)]^T$ and $\mathbf{g}(n) = [g(0), \dots, g(K-1)]^T$ is a vector of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) complex Gaussian random variables with zero mean and variance σ_g^2 .

3 RECEIVED CODE MATRIX ESTIMATION

Our aim is to compute an estimate of the received code matrix, $\mathbf{D}$, in the ML sense, from an available set of K observation vectors, $\mathbf{x}(0), \dots, \mathbf{x}(K-1)$. Blind estimation of $\mathbf{D}$ can be achieved by solving the optimization problem

$$\hat{\mathbf{D}} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{D}} \{ \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{D}) = E_{\mathbf{x}} \log(f_{\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{D}}(\mathbf{x})) \} \quad (4)$$

where $f_{\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{D}}(\cdot)$ is the p.d.f. of a single observation vector (that depends on the parameter matrix $\mathbf{D}$), $\log(\cdot)$ is the natural logarithm, $E_{\mathbf{x}(n)}$ denotes statistical expectation with respect to (w.r.t.) the random vector $\mathbf{x}(n)$ and $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{D})$ is the *expected log-likelihood* function of $\mathbf{D}$. Thus, $\hat{\mathbf{D}}$ will be referred as the Maximum Expected Likelihood (MEL) estimate of the received code matrix. Assuming that the AWGN is independent of the received symbols, the observations p.d.f. is

$$f_{\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{D}}(\mathbf{x}(n)) = \frac{1}{\pi^L \sigma_g^L} E_{\mathbf{s}} e^{-\frac{1}{\sigma_g^2} \|\mathbf{x}(n) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{s}\|^2} \quad (5)$$

where $E_{\mathbf{s}}$ denotes expectation w.r.t. the received symbol vector, $\mathbf{s}$, and $\|\mathbf{v}\|^2 = \mathbf{v}^H \mathbf{v}$. Substituting (5) into (4) yields the equivalent optimization problem

$$\hat{\mathbf{D}} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{D}} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{D}) = E_{\mathbf{x}} \log \left(E_{\mathbf{s}} e^{-\frac{1}{\sigma_g^2} \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{s}\|^2} \right) \right\}. \quad (6)$$

The inner expectation, $E_{\mathbf{s}}$, can be analytically calculated because, in digital communications, the transmitted symbols are usually modelled as finite alphabet discrete random variables with known p.d.f. Unfortunately, there is not a tractable closed-form expression for the outer expectation, $E_{\mathbf{x}}$, and, as a consequence, it must be estimated from the received observations. This estimation is both simplified and improved if we assume that a portion of the transmitted symbols are known *a priori*, as it happens in currently standardized mobile communication systems. When the first M symbols from each user are known and $E_{\mathbf{x}}$ is approximated by a time average, we arrive at the *semiblind* MEL estimator

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{D}} &= \arg \max_{\mathbf{D}} \left\{ -\frac{1}{\sigma_g^2} \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} \|\mathbf{x}(n) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{s}(n)\|^2 + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{n=M}^{K-1} \log \left(E_{\mathbf{s}} e^{-\frac{1}{\sigma_g^2} \|\mathbf{x}(n) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{s}\|^2} \right) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

3.1 EM Algorithm

Since the solution to (7) cannot be found analytically, we propose to numerically approximate $\hat{\mathbf{D}}$ by means of the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm [4]. The EM approach postulates the existence of some unobserved data that, if known, would aid in the estimation problem. Thus, the actual observations are termed *incomplete* data whereas the complete data set is defined as the union of the observed and unobserved data. The algorithm consists of two iterative steps: use of the incomplete data and the current parameter estimate to compute sufficient statistics of the complete data (E step) and re-estimate the parameters using the complete data sufficient statistics (M step). The resulting sequence of parameter estimates exhibit the property of being monotonically non decreasing in likelihood [4]. Global convergence, however, is not guaranteed when the likelihood function presents multiple local maxima.

In our problem, the incomplete data set is given by the received observation vectors, $\mathbf{x}(n)$, $n = 0, \dots, K - 1$, and the complete data set is denoted by $\mathbf{x}_e(n) = [\underline{\mathbf{s}}^T(n) \ \mathbf{x}^T(n)]^T$. The complete data sufficient statistics function is

$$U(\mathbf{D}, \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i) = \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} E_{\mathbf{x}_e(n) | \mathbf{x}(n), \underline{\mathbf{S}}; \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i} \log (f_{\mathbf{x}_e; \mathbf{D}}(\mathbf{x}_e(n))) \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_i$ is the i -th received code matrix estimate; $\mathbf{x}_e(n) | \mathbf{x}(n), \underline{\mathbf{S}}$ denotes conditioning of the complete data to both the incomplete data and the matrix $\underline{\mathbf{S}} = [\underline{\mathbf{s}}(0), \dots, \underline{\mathbf{s}}(M-1)]$ that contains the *a priori* known

symbols; function $f_{\mathbf{x}_e}(\cdot)$ is the complete data p.d.f.,

$$f_{\mathbf{x}_e; \mathbf{D}}(\mathbf{x}_e(n)) = \frac{1}{\pi^L \sigma_g^L} e^{-\frac{1}{\sigma_g^2} \|\mathbf{x}(n) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{s}(n)\|^2} f_{\mathbf{s}}(\mathbf{s}(n)), \quad (9)$$

and $f_{\mathbf{s}(n)}(\cdot)$ is the p.d.f. of the received symbol vectors. During the $(i+1)$ -th iteration, the E step consists of computing $U(\mathbf{D}, \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i)$ and the M step is

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{D}}_{i+1} &= \arg \max_{\mathbf{D}} \left\{ U(\mathbf{D}, \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i) \right\} \\ &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{D}} \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^{K-1} E_{\mathbf{s}(n)|\mathbf{x}(n), \underline{\mathbf{s}}; \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i} \|\mathbf{x}(n) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{s}(n)\|^2 \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Problem (10) is purely quadratic and presents a single closed-form solution

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{D}}_{i+1} &= \left(\sum_{n=0}^{K-1} E_{\mathbf{s}(n)|\mathbf{x}(n), \underline{\mathbf{s}}; \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i} \mathbf{s}(n) \mathbf{s}^H(n) \right)^{-1} \times \\ &\times \left(\sum_{n=0}^{K-1} E_{\mathbf{s}(n)|\mathbf{x}(n), \underline{\mathbf{s}}; \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i} \mathbf{s}(n) \mathbf{x}^H(n) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

So far, we have cast (7), which does not have an analytical solution, into a sequence of quadratic problems. In order to implement algorithm (11), however, the conditional *a posteriori* p.d.f. $f_{\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}(n); \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i}(\cdot)$ has to be known. The Bayes theorem allows to express this function in terms of the *a priori* p.d.f.'s $f_{\mathbf{x}; \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i}(\cdot)$ and $f_{\mathbf{s}}(\cdot)$, together with the conditional probability $f_{\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}(n); \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i}(\cdot)$ that is easily computed from eq. (5). As a result, the following relationship is obtained for $n \geq M$

$$E_{\mathbf{s}(n)|\mathbf{x}(n); \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i} \phi(\mathbf{s}(n)) = \frac{E_{\mathbf{s}(n)} e^{-\frac{1}{\sigma_g^2} \|\mathbf{x}(n) - \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i^H \mathbf{s}(n)\|^2} \phi(\mathbf{s}(n))}{E_{\mathbf{s}(n)} e^{-\frac{1}{\sigma_g^2} \|\mathbf{x}(n) - \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i^H \mathbf{s}(n)\|^2}} \quad (12)$$

where $\phi(\mathbf{s}(n))$ is an arbitrary function of $\mathbf{s}(n)$.

Although it is well known that the EM algorithm suffers from local misconvergence problems [4], our computer simulations show that very short training sequences are enough to practically guarantee that the received codes are accurately estimated (see section 5). The main limitation of algorithm (11) is not convergence, but computational complexity. Substituting (12) into (11), it can be seen that the proposed EM estimation algorithm complexity is $O(V^{Nm})$, where $\log_2(V)$ is the number of bits per symbol in the modulation format.

3.2 Decision Directed EM Algorithm

An important complexity reduction can be achieved if we realize that the conditional expectation $E_{\mathbf{s}(n)|\mathbf{x}(n); \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i} \mathbf{s}(n)$ is actually the Nonlinear Mean Squares (NMS) estimate [5] of $\mathbf{s}(n)$ obtained from the corresponding observations, $\mathbf{x}(n)$, and the i -th code matrix estimate, $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_i$. Therefore, it is sensible to substitute $E_{\mathbf{s}(n)|\mathbf{x}(n); \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i} \mathbf{s}(n)$ and $E_{\mathbf{s}(n)|\mathbf{x}(n); \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i} \mathbf{s}(n) \mathbf{s}^H(n)$ by $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i(n)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i(n) \hat{\mathbf{s}}_i^H(n)$, respectively, where $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i(n)$

is an estimate of $\mathbf{s}(n)$ computed using $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_i$. As a result, a Decision Directed EM (DDEM) algorithm is obtained that combines both symbol detection and channel estimation,

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i(n) = \text{Detect}(\mathbf{x}(n), \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i), \quad n = M, \dots, K-1 \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{D}}_{i+1} &= \left(\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} \mathbf{s}(n) \mathbf{s}^H(n) + \sum_{n=M}^{K-1} \hat{\mathbf{s}}_i(n) \hat{\mathbf{s}}_i^H(n) \right)^{-1} \times \\ &\left(\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} \mathbf{s}(n) \mathbf{x}^H(n) + \sum_{n=M}^{K-1} \hat{\mathbf{s}}_i(n) \mathbf{x}^H(n) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The computational complexity of the DDEM algorithm is mainly dependent on the scheme that is employed in the detection stage. An obvious choice is to use a linear multiuser detector (e.g., the linear Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) or the decorrelating detectors [2]) in order to achieve a good trade-off between computational load and performance.

Decision driven algorithms are usually very sensitive to the choice of the initial conditions and their performance may degrade severely as a consequence of the error propagation phenomenon. In our case, the initial received code matrix estimate, $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_0$, can be computed from the length M training sequence and the simulations in section 5 show that very few symbols are enough to ensure a fair performance.

4 JOINT ML MULTIUSER DETECTION

Let us define the transmitted symbol frame to be detected as $\underline{\mathbf{s}} = [\underline{\mathbf{s}}^T(M) \quad \dots \quad \underline{\mathbf{s}}^T(K-1)]^T$ and the corresponding received data frame $\underline{\mathbf{x}} = [\mathbf{x}^T(M) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{x}^T(K-1)]^T$. Optimum detection of the transmitted symbols is achieved by maximizing the *a posteriori* probability $f_{\underline{\mathbf{s}}|\underline{\mathbf{x}}}(\underline{\mathbf{s}})$ [2]. When all symbol frames are equiprobable, however, the maximum *a posteriori* detector reduces to the ML detector

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\underline{\mathbf{s}}}_{ML} &= \arg \max_{\underline{\mathbf{s}}} \left\{ f_{\underline{\mathbf{s}}|\underline{\mathbf{x}}; \hat{\mathbf{D}}}(\underline{\mathbf{x}}) \right\} \\ &= \arg \min_{\underline{\mathbf{s}}} \left\{ \Theta_{ML}(\underline{\mathbf{s}}) = \|\underline{\mathbf{x}} - \hat{\mathbf{D}} \underline{\mathbf{s}}_p\|^2 \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{s}}_p = [\underline{\mathbf{s}}^T(M-m+1) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{s}^T(M-1) \quad \underline{\mathbf{s}}^T]^T$ is the *padded* symbol frame and the $L(K-M) \times N(K-M+m-1)$ estimated received code matrix $\hat{\mathbf{D}}$ is constructed as

$$\hat{\mathbf{D}}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(m-1) & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(m-2) & \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(m-1) & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(m-2) & \ddots & \vdots \\ \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(0) & \vdots & \ddots & \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(m-1) \\ \vdots & \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(0) & \ddots & \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(m-2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \dots & \dots & \hat{\mathbf{D}}^T(0) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Figure 2: BER for several SNR values.

The ML metric $\Theta_{ML}(\cdot)$ admits the additive decomposition

$$\Theta_{ML}(\underline{\mathbf{s}}) = \sum_{n=M}^{K-1} \|\mathbf{x}(n) - \hat{\mathbf{D}}\mathbf{s}(n)\|^2 \quad (16)$$

that allows to employ a constrained-complexity trellis-search algorithm (e.g., the Viterbi algorithm) [2] to solve (15). Furthermore, it is interesting to note that the quadratic terms in (16) have already been computed in the channel estimation process, therefore reducing the complexity of the detection stage.

5 COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

We have carried out computer simulations to illustrate the performance of the proposed semiblind demodulators in an asynchronous DS CDMA system with $N = 3$ users, length $L = 6$ random binary spreading codes and length $P = 6$ complex unknown randomly chosen user channels. Each user transmits data frames containing $K = 150$ symbols, including $M = 10$ that are known *a priori* by the receiver. These training symbols are used to compute an initial Least Squares (LS) estimate, $\mathbf{D}_0$, of the received code matrix. After the final estimate $\hat{\mathbf{D}}$ is obtained, either with (11) or (14), the Viterbi algorithm is used for ML detection of the transmitted symbols. The decisions in the DDEM algorithm are obtained with a joint linear MMSE detector.

Figure 2 plots the Bit Error Rate (BER) achieved for several values of the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), defined as

$$\text{SNR} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{Trace}(\mathbf{D}^H \mathbf{D}) \sigma_s^2}{N \sigma_g^2} \right), \quad (17)$$

where σ_s^2 is the transmitted symbol power (equal for all users). The curve labeled *Viterbi* corresponds to the optimum receiver that carries out ML detection with perfect knowledge of the received code matrix. The curves labeled *EM-Viterbi* and *DDEM-Viterbi* correspond to the semiblind demodulators that perform

ML detection using the estimate of the received code computed with algorithms (11) and (14), respectively. The curve corresponding to the conventional *trained* ML detector that only exploits the *a priori* known symbols to estimate the received code matrix is labeled *LS-Viterbi*.

It is apparent that the conventional trained receiver attains a very poor performance because $M = 10$ symbols per user are not enough for an accurate estimation of the received codes. Thus, it is clearly outperformed by the proposed semiblind demodulators. It can be seen that the MEL estimation of the received codes with the EM algorithm is accurate enough to achieve practically optimum performance. The DDEM algorithm, on the other hand, exhibits a higher BER, but also requires a lower computational load.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A novel semiblind multiuser demodulation scheme has been introduced that leads to practically optimum performance in time dispersive DS CDMA channels. Demodulation is carried out in two stages: (a) semiblind channel identification in the ML sense using the EM algorithm and (b) ML symbol detection with a dynamic programming algorithm (e.g., the Viterbi algorithm). In addition, a decision driven EM algorithm, with lower computational requirements, has been also proposed.

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